

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Deliverable D1.6

Plan for the Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication Activities Update

Planned delivery date: 30/11/2023 (M18)

Actual submission date: 29/11/2023 (M18)

Deliverable leader: 2- ERINN

Authors: Sarah Sarsfield (ERINN Innovation), Maura Lynskey (ERINN Innovation)

Type of deliverable: Report

Work package Leader: WP1 – Ifremer

Version: 2.0

Project funded by the European Commission within the HORIZON-MISS-2021-OCEAN-01	
Dissemination Level	
PU Public	X
PP Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO Confidential, only for member of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

GA No. 101056957 - PREP4BLUE

Start date of the project: June 1st, 2022

www.Prepare4Blue.eu

Funded by the European Union, through its Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101056957 (PREP4BLUE). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the granting authority, the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

DISCLAIMER

“PREP4BLUE: Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters” has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Program call “Preparation for deployment of ‘lighthouse demonstrators’ and solution scale ups and cross-cutting citizen and stakeholder involvement (HORIZON-MISS-2021-OCEAN-01)”, Grant Agreement n° 101056957.

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the granting authority, the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This document contains information on PREP4BLUE core activities. Any reference to content in this document should clearly indicate the authors, source, organisation, and publication date. The authors of this document have taken any available measure in order for its content to be accurate, consistent and lawful. However, neither the project consortium as a whole nor the individual partners that implicitly or explicitly participated in the creation and publication of this document hold any sort of responsibility that might occur as a result of using its content.

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

This work by Parties of the PREP4BLUE Consortium is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). “PREP4BLUE: Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters” has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Program call HORIZON-MISS-2021-OCEAN-01, Grant Agreement n. 101056957.

VERSIONING AND CONTRIBUTION HISTORY

Version	Date	Authors (Institution)	Summary of changes made
D1.2 v0.1	19.10.2022	Cliona Ní Cheallacháin, (ERINN Innovation)	N/A
D1.2 v1.0	28.11.2022	Sarah Sarsfield, Cliona Ni Cheallachain (ERINN Innovation)	Feedback received from coordination implemented
D1.6 v0.1	01.11.23	Sarah Sarsfield, Maura Lynskey (ERINN Innovation)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • History of revisions table added • Edits to Introduction text to reflect new version of PDEC and work completed • Additional communications resources added to Table 2 • Brand guidelines added to Dissemination Resources list • Funding Acknowledgement Image (EU Flag) updated to most recent version

Version	Date	Authors (Institution)	Summary of changes made
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous Reporting Procedures updated • OurMissionOcean Twitter handle updated • Note on updating communication resources to reflect Twitter name change added • Update to ERINN contact details • Typographical edits made throughout document • Correction of formatting errors and structure throughout document where needed • Appendix I moved to start of document and renamed, additional abbreviations added • Appendix II added
D1.6 v0.2	22.11.2023	Emma Bello Gómez (EuroMarine)	Coordination review
D1.6 v0.2	23.11.2023	Cécile Nys (Ifremer)	Coordination review

Table of Contents

TABLE OF CONTENTS	4
TABLE OF FIGURES	6
ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS	7
1. INTRODUCTION	8
1.1 OVERVIEW	8
1.2 OBJECTIVES	9
2. STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT	9
2.1 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT STRATEGY	9
<i>2.1.1 End-users of Prep4Blue’s KERs</i>	<i>11</i>
2.2 CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT - MISSION NARRATIVE	16
3. KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT, TRANSFER & EXPLOITATION OF RESULTS	16
3.1 KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT & TRANSFER OVERVIEW	16
3.2 KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT AND TRANSFER	18
3.3 PHASE 1: COLLECT & UNDERSTAND – KNOWLEDGE COLLECTION	19
3.4 PHASE 2: ANALYSE & VALIDATE	20
3.5 PHASE 3: TRANSFER AND EXPLOIT	22
4. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES	24
5. PREP4BLUE-SPECIFIC STAKEHOLDER EVENTS	26
5.1 CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT	26
5.2 PHYSICAL AND VIRTUAL MISSION SPACES	26
5.3 CO-CREATION EVENTS	26
5.4 PILOT STAKEHOLDER ASSEMBLIES FOR THE MISSION	27
6. EXTERNAL EVENTS	27
7. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION RESOURCES	28
7.1 LOGO	28
7.2 PREP4BLUE PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS	29
7.3 PRESS RELEASES AND NEWSLETTERS	30
7.4 PROJECT WEBSITE	31
7.5 SOCIAL MEDIA	31
7.6 PROJECT VIDEO	33
7.7 OTHER RESOURCES AND TOOLS	33
8. REQUIREMENTS RELATED TO DISSEMINATION	34
8.1 PRE-DISSEMINATION REQUIREMENTS	34
8.2 POST-DISSEMINATION REQUIREMENTS	34
<i>8.2.1 Continuous Reporting of Dissemination and Communication Activities</i>	<i>34</i>
<i>8.2.2 Continuous Reporting of Scientific Publications</i>	<i>35</i>
8.2.3 Datasets	36
8.2.4 Patents (IPR) Reporting	36
9. KEY PRINCIPLES GUIDING THE PDEC	37

9.1	DEFINITIONS AND TERMINOLOGY.....	37
9.2	RIGHTS, RULES AND OBLIGATIONS RELATED TO RESULTS.....	37
	9.2.1 <i>Ownership of Results</i>	38
	9.2.2 <i>Protection of Results</i>	38
	9.2.3 <i>Exploitation of Results</i>	38
	9.2.4 <i>Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and Management</i>	38
9.3	DISSEMINATION OF RESULTS	38
	9.3.1 <i>Obligation to Dissemination</i>	38
	9.3.2 <i>Open Access</i>	39
	9.3.3 <i>Visibility of EU emblem</i>	40
9.4	GENERAL DATA PROTECTION REGULATION IMPLICATIONS	40
	9.4.1 <i>Website</i>	40
10.	MONITORING AND EVALUATION	41
11.	PARTNERS INVOLVED IN THE WORK	41

Table of figures

TABLE 1. TABLE OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS USED IN PREP4BLUE AND THE DOCUMENT	7
TABLE 2. PREP4BLUE STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT STRATEGY	12
TABLE 3. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES AND RESOURCES.....	25
TABLE 4. RELEVANT EVENTS FOR PREP4BLUE CONSORTIUM AND STAKEHOLDERS.	28
TABLE 5. OVERVIEW OF CONTINUOUS REPORTING PROCEDURES.....	36
FIGURE 1. PREP4BLUE KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER METHODOLOGY.....	19
FIGURE 2. PREP4BLUE KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER METHODOLOGY: COLLECT AND UNDERSTAND.....	19
FIGURE 3. PREP4BLUE KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER METHODOLOGY: ANALYSE AND VALIDATE	21
FIGURE 4. PREP4BLUE LOGO.....	29

Acronyms & Abbreviations

Table 1. Table of abbreviations and acronyms used in Prep4Blue and the document

Acronym / Abbreviation	Signification
CSA	Coordinator & Support Action
D#.#	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IA	Innovation Action
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KMS	Knowledge Management System
KO	Knowledge Output
KP	Knowledge Output Pathway
KOT	Knowledge Output Template
KT	Knowledge Transfer
KTP	Knowledge Transfer Plan
LH	Lighthouse
M#	Milestone
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PDEC	Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
R&I	Research and Innovation
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
T#.#	Task
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The PREP4BLUE Plan for the Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication Activities (PDEC) outlines the EC rights and obligations of the consortium related to exploitation, dissemination, and communication of project results. It adopts EC best practice guidelines and defines the objectives of PREP4BLUE's plans for communication, dissemination, and exploitation. It also identifies target stakeholders, proposes communication tools and channels, and outlines responsibilities and resources to carry out effective knowledge management and to measure impact of activities carried out.

The PDEC has been developed by ERINN Innovation, who will also oversee its continuous implementation. The PDEC is a living document and will be updated regularly throughout the project. The first iteration of this document (D1.2) was submitted in November 2022 (M6), it will be updated again in M18 (D1.6) and at the end of the project in M36 (D1.9).

All project partners have an obligation to participate in the dissemination and exploitation of PREP4BLUE results as well as outputs and to foster awareness and transfer results for impact, especially in their own countries and in their own communities. Within the PDEC the dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities to be performed are described, along with protocols and processes to be followed.

Within PREP4BLUE there are two Work Packages (WPs) with communication activities, which have been designed to support project communication activities, target a range of audiences and stakeholders communicating key messages about the project and the Mission. Each one has specific and defined objectives, tasks and deliverables. In summary:

- Task 1.5 in WP1 will focus on external communication and dissemination of the PREP4BLUE project results and outputs, with a specific focus on other initiatives contributing to the Mission (CSAs, IAs, RIAs, etc).
- WP2 will communicate Mission Ocean to the general public and provide resources and support to PREP4BLUE partners and other relevant stakeholders seeking to share their stories in order to more fully engage and invite public participation in the Mission. WP2 will provide helpful tools such as a narrative guide and communication plan, and pilot a social media campaign, website, and events meant to support partners while engaging the public, inspiring awe and wonder around the ocean, and encouraging understanding of, and active participation in, Mission Ocean.

To support partners in communication, dissemination and exploitation of results, a portfolio of resources will also be developed under WP1. This portfolio will be updated regularly throughout the project (D1.4). PREP4BLUE will make use of the latest tools and communication channels to ensure cost effectiveness and maximum impact.

1.1 Overview

Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters (the Mission) aims to restore the health of our ocean and waters by 2030, as a major contributor to the European Green Deal and the Sustainable Development Goals. Research and innovation will be a key component of the Mission, which will

link initiatives across disciplines, mobilise policymakers, stakeholders and citizens, and leverage public and private investments.

PREP4BLUE's overarching objective is to facilitate a successful first phase (2022-2025) of the Mission, by developing the co-creation and co-implementation of Research and Innovation (R&I) modalities required to achieve the Mission objectives and preparing the ground for inspiring and engaging citizens and stakeholders.

The project is designed to deliver a series of tools, guidelines, methodologies and recommendations tested through pilots, which will interlink, leverage and optimise activities among the projects funded under the Mission. PREP4BLUE's systemic approach will foster cohesion and connectivity between knowledge and technology, funding, regulation, education and skills, social structures and co-creation with R&I actors, citizens and stakeholders.

To guarantee the adoption of PREP4BLUE solutions, and to maximise the impacts of PREP4BLUE results, the project has put in place effective communication, dissemination, engagement and knowledge transfer strategies as part of 'WP1 - Project Coordination, Synergies, Communication'.

1.2 Objectives

The PDEC aims to:

- Identify and profile target groups for the different project results.
- Propose the most effective tools and channels to respond to the needs of the relevant stakeholders.
- Outline the PREP4BLUE knowledge management system and knowledge transfer principles and protocols to ensure effective transfer and exploitation of its Key Exploitable Results (KERs).
- Outline the IP protection strategy and intellectual property rights (IPR) management system, in line with the Grant Agreement and project Data Management Plan where relevant.
- Support consortium members in transferring PREP4BLUE results by defining impact pathways and validating transfer strategies embedded in tasks across WPs.

2. Stakeholder Engagement

The purpose of the engagement activities described in the PREP4BLUE PDEC is to facilitate dialogue, build relationships and generate exchanges between PREP4BLUE and relevant stakeholders as described below.

2.1 Stakeholder Engagement Strategy

To engage with its stakeholders for the purpose of transferring project result and outputs, PREP4BLUE will implement structured knowledge management and transfer methodology. By focusing on Individual Outputs and associated Transfer Plans, appropriate target and end- users

will be identified, along with potential application and exploitation routes, as is outlined in the Knowledge Transfer Methodology (Section 3).

Stakeholder engagement takes many shapes, depending on the context, in the activities of PREP4BLUE:

WP1. The Mission Charter¹ has become an important implementation tool and its adoption by stakeholders a major criterion for the evaluation of the Ocean Mission in June 2023. The PREP4BLUE Network of stakeholders (Task 1.3) represents an opportunity to promote the Mission Charter. Task 1.3 will identify relevant actions, projects and initiatives contributing to the Mission, as defined by the Mission charter², and will promote and support them to submit pledges to the Charter.

- ➔ Stakeholders in T1.3 = actions, as defined in the Mission charter, which contribute to the Mission objectives, which submit pledges to the Mission charter and become **Stakeholders of the charter.**

WP 3, 5 and 6. These work packages will develop methodologies and tools that will allow all stakeholders to engage with the Mission. WP3 will address citizen engagement, WP5 will address the regulatory, financial and business engagement and WP6 will adopt the 'Penta-Helix Model', which includes industry/businesses, public authorities, citizens/local residents, academia/the knowledge sector and associations, and which builds upon a culture of collaboration and recognition of the environment as fundamental for social innovation. The methodologies and tools developed for stakeholder engagement will target two different objectives:

- ➔ To involve **stakeholders in research and innovation projects** that contribute to the Mission objectives = the methodologies and tools for stakeholder engagement will be addressed to coordinators of R&I/IA projects that need to develop co-creation and co-implementation procedures for their scientific work. Stakeholders of a research project can be defined as the actors that can affect or are affected by the knowledge produced by the research.
- ➔ To involve a wide **community of stakeholders for the development of new social and innovation ecosystem in each basin (Lighthouses of the Mission)** = the methodologies and tools for stakeholder engagement will be addressed to coordinators of CSAs and/or Mission governance structures with a role in the establishment of the Lighthouses.

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/MissionOceanWatersCharter>

² Actions include policies, programmes, initiatives and projects to support:

- Research and innovation;
- Evidence-based knowledge and data and/or access provision to knowledge and data, in line with FAIR principles for the Mission Ocean and Waters Knowledge System;
- Upscaling, deployment and replication of solutions;
- Citizen engagement, citizens-science, youth-led initiatives, communities of practice, ocean and water literacy, outreach, awareness raising and participatory approaches;
- Education and training.

The consortium has extensive experience in multinational, multi-lingual, multi-disciplinary and multi-partner collaborative research and innovation activities, and in effective communication of progress and results. By applying the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy, we have identified the various groups in society, listed below (2.1.1), to have a vested interest in the PREP4BLUE results.

2.1.1 End-users of Prep4Blue's KERs

The likely end-users of PREP4BLUE KERs include:

- **Mission governance actors:** Mission manager, Deputy-mission manager, Mission Secretariat, CINEA executive agency, Commission-internal Mission owners group, Implementation support platform, Mission Lighthouse CSAs (1 per basin), Other Missions and Mission National Hubs– Engagement via TRAMI project.
- **Activities contributing to the Mission objectives:** R&I and IA projects at regional/local, national and European level (dedicated topics in the Mission Work programmes and other Work programmes). Other European Initiatives (e.g. Partnerships, Smart specialisation strategies), Other Global Initiatives (UN Decades). Other National, regional actors and networks.
- **Academics and Scientists:** actors in the areas of seas/oceans, freshwater and the environment.
- **Policymakers:** Policymakers at local, regional, national and EU level in the areas of seas/oceans, freshwater and the environment.
- **Business/Industry:** Business owners and Industry stakeholders in the areas of seas/oceans, freshwater and the environment.
- **Public and Private funders:** Public funders responsible for the administration of EU, national and regional funding, Private funders (venture capitalists, companies, banks, philanthropists and foundations).
- **Citizens and society as a whole:** Members of the general public, especially those from coastal and/or riparian communities, Citizen Engagement Networks with a focus on seas/oceans and freshwater (Ocean Literacy Networks, Living laboratories, Coastal/Riparian initiatives, citizen science groups), Not for Profits (ocean and freshwater advocacy groups, NGOs, community-led local development organizations, youth groups and forums), citizen assemblies.

The PREP4BLUE Stakeholder Engagement Strategy is outlined below in Table 1. It includes the objectives, activities and expected impact of engagement per main stakeholder group throughout the full project duration.

Table 2. PREP4BLUE Stakeholder Engagement Strategy

Target and user groups	Tools of Engagement /Outputs to Transfer	Expected Impact
Mission Governance Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Website • Project videos • Project newsletter • Workshops • Participatory events • Mission Ecosystem Database and Mission ontology • Knowledge Management methodology • Mission Website • Guides on communicating the Mission • Social media • Guidelines on how to engage stakeholders for creating a new social and innovation ecosystem in each basin (Lighthouses) • Recommendations on how to fund scale-up solutions beyond 2025 • Roadmap to success for future LH projects • Critical assessment and key recommendations for inter-regional financing • Vision of how to fund scale up solutions beyond 2025 • Business interaction models for mission scale-up • Business model blueprints and de-risking recommendations • Guidelines on supporting Citizen Participation to achieve the Mission • Mission Lighthouse Helpdesk 	<p>Raise awareness of PREP4BLUE actions and activities, while also raising awareness of the Mission itself, its aims, goals and objectives. In particular, focus on how to transfer PREP4BLUE outputs to other Mission contributors in order to increase efficiency.</p>
Academia and research <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marine biologists • Freshwater scientists 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Website • Publications • Presentations at conferences 	<p>Transfer of knowledge, raise awareness, reuse of the scientific data, boost the</p>

Target and user groups	Tools of Engagement /Outputs to Transfer	Expected Impact
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate scientists • Social scientists and • Environmental scientists • Economists • Sustainable Finance • Early Career Researchers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other events • Mission website • Mission Ecosystem Database and Mission ontology • Knowledge Management methodology • Case studies of successful Knowledge Transfer • Tools and methods for stakeholder and citizens engagement in research (penta-helix model) • Helpdesk • Community of practices • Business model blueprints and de-risking recommendations • Guidelines on supporting Citizen Participation to achieve the Mission • Series of capacity building workshops around the theme “Supporting citizen participation in Mission Ocean and Waters”. • Recordings of select citizen participation workshops uploaded to website as training resource. • Inventory of Marine and Freshwater Citizen Science Initiatives across Europe • Portfolio of pilot citizen engagement activities to support evaluation of tools and methods. 	<p>project sustainability through the development of new related research projects. Increase pledges for the Mission charter</p>
<p>Funding Bodies and Policy makers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public funders (EU, National, Regional) • Private funders (Venture capitalists, companies, banks, philanthropy) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Website • Project videos • Project newsletter • Mission Ecosystem Database • Knowledge Management methodology • Case Studies of successful Knowledge Transfer • Mission Website • Workshops • Business models and recommendations for interregional financing 	<p>Raise awareness of the Mission, its aims, goals and objectives, and thus raise awareness of aquatic resources and value chains amongst public and private funding bodies and investors; all in order to enable and drive coherent, integrated funding and investments for Mission-driven innovation and solutions scale-up post 2025.</p>

Target and user groups	Tools of Engagement /Outputs to Transfer	Expected Impact
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy makers at local, regional, national and EU level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solutions to better address regulatory barriers • Vision of how to fund scale up solutions beyond 2025 • Business interaction models for mission scale-up • Guidelines on supporting Citizen Participation to achieve the Mission 	<p>Increase pledges for the Mission charter</p>
<p>Industry</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ocean, marine, freshwater, environment focused companies • Research focused companies • Fishing and aquaculture industry • Related local businesses, SMEs and start-ups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Website • Project Videos • Project Newsletter • Mission Ecosystem Database • Knowledge Management methodology • Case studies of successful Knowledge Transfer • Mission Website • Participatory events • Business model blueprint and de-risking recommendations 	<p>Raise awareness of the Mission, its aims, goals and objectives, and thus raise awareness of aquatic resources and value chains amongst different industries with links to the Ocean and Waters.</p> <p>Increase pledges for the Mission charter</p>
<p>Citizens</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coastal/Riparian communities • Youth groups • Citizen Interest Groups • Citizen Engagement Networks • Society as whole (general public) • Citizen science initiatives • Ocean Literacy Networks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen science pilots • Community Engagement activities • Promotional material • Project Website • Project Videos • Series of capacity building workshops around the theme “Supporting citizen participation in Mission Ocean and Waters”. • Recordings of select citizen participation workshops uploaded to website as training resource. • Art engagement and exhibition • Factsheets in relevant • Languages • Social media 	<p>Increase citizens awareness, participation and engagement in the mission and its activities. Communicate the value and need to protect our seas, oceans and waters now and in the future, demonstrating how this will contribute to a better and more resilient society.</p>

Target and user groups	Tools of Engagement /Outputs to Transfer	Expected Impact
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Voluntary Community Groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On-the-ground training events • Inventory of Marine and Freshwater Citizen Science Initiatives across Europe • Portfolio of pilot citizen engagement activities to support evaluation of tools and methods. • Network of citizen action • Mission and project information supplied alongside needs analysis survey • Mission website • Guidelines on supporting Citizen Participation to achieve the Mission 	

2.2 Citizen Engagement - Mission Narrative

A key objective of WP2 is to develop and maintain communication tools for PREP4BLUE partners and establish visionary narrative for the Mission by spotlighting project stories via social media, a website and events – all meant to engage and inspire the public to join Mission Ocean. The tools developed by WP2 include a narrative guide and communication plan to support PREP4BLUE partners and other Mission stakeholders in their storytelling while adhering to Mission Ocean branding for a unified and cohesive effort. Additionally, a Mission Ocean website, various social media channels and events is being piloted to engage the public in Mission Ocean, while providing PREP4BLUE partners platforms to share their results and stories. It is hoped that the social media channels and website could be used as an “official” unifying Mission Ocean platforms to engage the public to save time, effort, and resources from Mission stakeholders who feel obligated to “recreate the wheel.”

3. Knowledge Management, Transfer & Exploitation of Results

3.1 Knowledge Management & Transfer Overview

The European Commission has identified the importance of improving knowledge transfer between public research institutions and third parties, including industry and civil society organisations, as one of ten key areas for action³. As part of T1.5, PREP4BLUE will employ a proven Knowledge Management and Transfer methodology to effectively address this key aspect of facilitating project impact.

This methodology was originally developed in the FP7 MarineTT project (GA #244164), and further developed and applied by the H2020 COLUMBUS project (GA #652690 - www.columbusproject.eu). This methodology has been applied in many FP7 and Horizon 2020 funded projects such as AQUAEXCEL, AQUAEXCEL2020, AqualInnova, ARRAINA, COEXIST, COMMON SENSE, ECsafeSEAFOOD, MaCuMBA, MG4U, ParaFishControl, MATES, SIMBA, ERGO REviveD water, RES4BUILD, SEALIVE, BIOGEARS, SEArcularMINE TechOceanS and WaterLANDS.

This methodology will also be utilised in PREP4BLUE WP4 to pilot how to effectively manage knowledge that could potentially contribute to the achievement of Mission objectives.

The key concepts used in the Knowledge Management and Transfer methodology are as follow:

- **Knowledge Management** is the process of identifying, capturing, organising, analysing, and storing knowledge to ensure its availability to be transferred effectively to specific and relevant users.
- **Knowledge Transfer (KT)** is the overall process of moving knowledge from knowledge sources to targeted potential users of the knowledge, focusing the research being conducted on the wider needs of society and industry. KT consists of a range of activities

³ https://ec.europa.eu/invest-in-research/pdf/download_en/knowledge_transfe_07.pdf

that aims to capture and transmit knowledge, skills, and competence from those who generate them to those who will transform them into added value outcomes. It encompasses both commercial and non-commercial activities such as research collaborations, consultancy, licensing, spin-off creation, researcher mobility, and publications. The ultimate end benefit of successful KT is the application and influence of knowledge on targeted communities with greater impact (short and long term) across academia, industry, and society.

- **Knowledge Outputs (KOs)** are described as “a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a scientific project. It is not limited to *de-novo* or pioneering discoveries but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior know-how/knowledge”. Typically, such knowledge might be referenced as a small part of a published paper, potentially three to five years after the approach is pioneered in a research project.
- **Key Exploitable Results (KERs)** within PREP4BLUE are tangible or intangible outputs of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature which have been deemed to be of **high priority** for project transfer actions. The means by which KERs will be identified from KOs is described in this section, but it is important to note that PREP4BLUE is not implying any sort of value judgement between KOs and KERs. Rather, the project is simply using this distinction to allow knowledge that is of the most direct impact to the project, or is most feasibly transferable by the project, to be prioritised when assigning resources for transfer. By focusing on identifying KERs and transferring them when they have been assessed as having potential application and impact, it is possible to fast track them, providing a faster impact on target- and end-users external to the project.
- **End User(s)** are the individual(s) who are identified as being in a position where they could feasibly **apply** a given unit of Knowledge (KO/KER) and by doing so create the desired eventual **impact** of that knowledge. The KO/KER may need to **evolve** in order to reach the end user.
- **Target User** is an individual(s) (organisations should be avoided where possible as specificity is crucial), whose position makes them a potential stepping-stone needed for a KO/KER to progress towards an identified end user and eventual impact. Target users are individuals with a specific mandate or responsibilities relevant to the specific KO/KER being evaluated. Target users should not merely be potential users of knowledge but should be individuals whose application of the knowledge is likely to advance it down the Pathway to Impact.
- A **Knowledge Transfer Plan (KTP)** is an informed stepwise plan for achieving the identified eventual impact of any piece of knowledge, regardless of whether this impact is achievable in the short, medium or long term. In PREP4BLUE these will be developed for all selected KERs. The KTP identifies the end user capable of producing the desired

eventual impact and outlines a specific series of transfer activities to intermediate target users.

- **Eventual Impact** is the ultimate end benefit of the application of the knowledge (KO/KER). It is defined as an overall enhanced situation, generally for society but it can also be research or industry specific. Eventual impacts can be the adoption of new technologies, products or innovation identified and refined within the project, or a change in protocols.

The Knowledge Management and Transfer of PREP4BLUE KERs is integrated into the project through WP1 and is based on regularly collecting KOs/KERs through structured templates and interviews with partners responsible for developing the results (See Appendix II for templates). Collected results will be assessed based on criteria related to their innovation capacity, relevance to the sector, and expected impact. Knowledge Transfer Plans (KTPs) will be developed for individual or clusters of KERs assessed as being of high potential for contributing to Mission objectives. This customised approach will increase the likelihood that 1) KERs will be transferred and exploited successfully, and the result applied; 2) there is an increased potential for impact from the transfer; and 3) it is possible to measure and demonstrate the impact of the transfer.

ERINN will coordinate and collaborate with other PREP4BLUE WPs to carry out KT. All partners will contribute to the project's Knowledge Management and Transfer activities by adhering to the protocols and assisting in the collection and analysis of KOs and the transfer of high potential KERs to end-users.

The Knowledge Management and Transfer methodology consists of the following three overall phases and is further described in detail below:

- Collect and Understand
- Validate and Analyse
- Transfer and Exploit

3.2 Knowledge Management and Transfer

This section of the PDEC outlines the stepwise process, which will be carried out within PREP4BLUE Tasks 4.3 and 4.4. This methodology will see KOs identified, collected, reviewed, and prioritised to project KERs with developed KTPs during three distinct steps: Collection & Understand, Validate & Analyse, Transfer & Exploit. The figure below outlines an example of a full Pathway to Impact.

Figure 1. PREP4BLUE Knowledge Transfer Methodology.

3.3 Phase 1: Collect & Understand – Knowledge collection

Phase One: Capturing of KOs in an internal KO template (KOT).

Effective KT relies on careful identification and description of KOs to ensure that all key information is provided which will result in effective transfer (Figure 2). Quality control measures will be performed, to ensure that the KO(s) can be clearly understood by others who may not be experts in the relevant disciplines. Each partner will treat information from other partners as confidential unless otherwise stated and not disclose it to other parties unless the information is publicly available. It is important for all beneficiaries to note that KOs are not only the final results of research, but they can also be part of the methodology to obtain the final result, which could be an innovation for a research area or process.

Phase one aims to understand the positioning of a KO to be better able to carry out impactful KT activities. It intends to help clarify how the KO could be beneficial to different targets and end users. This step identifies potential applications, target and end users and the eventual impact of a KO. This information will also inform the development of Knowledge Output Pathways (KOPs) of KOs that progress to being a KER having been assessed as having high potential application and impact.

Figure 2. PREP4BLUE Knowledge Transfer Methodology: Collect and Understand

It should be noted that KOs/KERs, especially those collected early in the project, are likely to continue to develop over the course of PREP4BLUE. Collected knowledge will be periodically reviewed by ERINN and partners asked to provide updates if applicable. As the collection template will be available on the project TEAMS, partners will be able to advise ERINN if a given KO/KER needs to be updated.

PROTOCOL – Collect & Understand

1. ERINN sends the Knowledge Output Template (KOT) to PREP4BLUE WP Leaders, who will be requested to complete it and update as necessary.
2. If the WP Leader thinks another partner is better placed to provide the requested information, then they should send it on to the relevant person(s).
3. For each identified KO, all fields of the KOT should be completed. Explanations are provided under each question.
4. Completed KOTs should be sent to ERINN.
5. ERINN arranges and conducts interviews with the KO owner(s) for clarity on the knowledge collected.
6. After the interview, the KO owner(s) will receive an updated draft of the KO to check for accuracy following on from the discussion.
7. KO owner(s) are requested to respond with any corrections or suggested additions/edits in a timely manner. In particular, this review should focus on:
 - If the title of the KO(s) is sufficiently informative.
 - If the description of the KO(s) is sufficiently comprehensive for a non-expert to adequately understand the nature of the KO and to determine its possible application.
 - If the potential end-users of the KO, as well as the potential application by each of these end users is reasonable/desirable and if there are any other potential end users.
 - If the KO(s) is supposed to be publicly available or is subject to IPR protection, which would influence transfer potential.
8. Once the interviewee is satisfied with the accuracy of their KOs they will be marked as “confirmed” in the KOT.
9. Once confirmed, an IP review will be carried out. This involves:
 - If an IP assessment is deemed necessary, the generating partner will be asked to complete an IP Assessment Form. Assessment Forms will be reviewed by ERINN, who will provide guidance as necessary until all relevant parties believe sufficient IP protection rules have been applied to the further dissemination, communication, and exploitation of the KO. Once the IP assessment is completed, or if an IP assessment is not deemed necessary, KOs will advance to the validation and analysis stage.

3.4 Phase 2: Analyse & Validate

Phase 2: The collected KOs are reviewed and assessed for potential application and impact.

Once validated, KOs go through a Due Diligence process, whereby a more thorough examination and evaluation of the KO and its applicability and readiness for transfer will be investigated (Figure 3). Due Diligence will be undertaken so that any factors that could affect the transfer

potential (confidentiality, competition, IPR) of the KO and ultimately the uptake and impact of the knowledge can be identified. Following Due Diligence, KOs will be prioritised and those with potential to have impact will go through to the next step. An essential step in the PREP4BLUE knowledge management and transfer methodology is the identification of KO applications, potential impact and respective end users (e.g., applications could be in various areas and sectors not just the one in the research area of the project) for each KO which has been assessed as having high potential application and impact.

Important aspects are prioritisation of high potential KOs and profiling target and end users to gain valuable data to inform successful Knowledge Transfer Plans. This is not a ranking of their importance but rather a method to help PREP4BLUE identify where to focus transfer and exploitation efforts. For those prioritised, the expert groups will attempt to identify potential target users whose application of the knowledge would be of benefit in transferring it towards its eventual impact.

Those KOs that are validated and deemed to be of priority for the project will be re-labelled as **Key Exploitable Results (KERs)** and progress to the third phase. Any KO that is not made a KER will continue to be periodically reviewed by WP4 and any remaining at the end of the project will still be captured as evidence of project results for final reporting. The identification of target users in the analysis stage is critical to laying the groundwork for transfer and exploitation plans in the third phase. The exercises in this phase may also serve to identify potential stakeholders worth connecting with, even in cases where the knowledge may not yet be ready for transfer.

Figure 3. PREP4BLUE Knowledge Transfer Methodology: Analyse and Validate

PROTOCOL – Analyse & Validate

At periodic intervals, ERINN will organise KO and KER “expert analysis meetings”.

- The frequency and makeup of these meetings will be determined in collaboration with the Project Coordinator as well as based on the current status of knowledge collection and management in the project.

The expert analysis meetings will carry out a thorough examination and evaluation of the KOs (collected so far) and their applicability and readiness for transfer. Particular attention will be paid to:

- Identification of all likely target and end-users. We encourage partners to be as specific as possible and innovative when determining potential end users.
- It is important to consider the following when profiling target and end users:
 - Understand the user's mandate or responsibilities.
 - Consider their background knowledge, attitude, and practice in relation to the issue.
 - Understand their knowledge needs.
 - Understand what and who may influence their decisions.
 - Be aware of their preferred sources of information and knowledge.
- Identification of associated application and impact potential.

Assess the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) that could inform the development of an appropriate KO Pathway, where KO requires further research, validation or scale-up.

Participants in these meetings will be asked to:

- Confirm the accuracy and feasibility of transfer both within and beyond the project (but as a direct result of the project) for each presented KO, to the best of their understanding.
- Assign to each KO a ranking to determine whether it should be prioritised as a KER based on its current status.
- Discuss and identify potential target users to whom the knowledge should be transferred to progress it towards its eventual impact.

After each expert analysis meeting, ERINN will revise the KOT to identify any progression of knowledge (such as a KO being changed to a KER).

If any questions emerge from the expert analysis meeting, ERINN will reach out to the relevant KO owners to attempt to provide an answer.

3.5 Phase 3: Transfer and Exploit

Phase 3: Carry out and report on Knowledge Transfer activities; while measuring the impact of both the activity and the application of the Knowledge by the User(s).

For each KER, a Knowledge Transfer Plan (KTP) will be developed. Implementing an efficient KTP that is tailor-made to the needs and capacities of specific target and end users (profiled in phase 2) will maximise the chance of successful transfer resulting in uptake and application. The key to success is achieved through fully understanding the target and end user and developing the KTP around them. There are a number of steps included in the knowledge transfer plan, and there are different routes it can go down to reach its eventual impact. KTPs are the accumulation of numerous KT activities as represented in Figure 4.

KTPs will ensure KERs go through a Due Diligence process, whereby a more thorough examination and evaluation of the KER and its applicability and readiness for transfer will be investigated. Due

Diligence will be undertaken so that any factors that could affect the transfer potential (confidentiality, competition, IPR) of the KER and ultimately the uptake and impact of the knowledge can be identified. The individual partner within PREP4BLUE best positioned to conduct the transfer will be identified and this phase will attempt to clearly describe how the impact of PREP4BLUE' KERs will be measured, even after the project has come to a close.

The work carried out in this phase will not only be important for accurately reporting the full breadth of impact of the project to the European Commission, but it will also assist all partners in carrying out exploitation activities. Not every KER transfer plan will be able to be reasonably executed during the lifetime of the project but, by delivering clear plans, the knowledge management methodology will help establish how exploitation actions within the project will feed into the overall impact of the project as a whole and help achieve the societal goals of PREP4BLUE.

Figure 4: PREP4BLUE Knowledge Transfer Methodology: Transfer and Exploit

PROTOCOL – Knowledge Transfer Planning & Exploitation

For any knowledge that has been determined to be a KER:

1. ERINN will collaborate with the executive committee and the owner(s) of a KER to develop a Knowledge Transfer Plan (KTP) for each KER. In particular, this effort will focus on the following considerations regarding the first target user(s) in the plan:
 - a. Building on the impact potential identified in the validation and analysis step, ensure that a concise and compelling narrative for the opportunity/business case is developed.
 - b. The technical level of the target user; the depth of information needed; and the style of language most effective for communicating with them.
 - c. The background knowledge of the target user.
 - d. Any preconceived ideas that the target user may have relating to the area of interest.
 - e. Ways in which to relate the knowledge to examples with which the target user is familiar, or ones they can easily envisage.
 - f. The level of evidence or validation that the target user requires.
2. ERINN will be responsible for drafting these plans, which will then be provided to the project management team, project coordinator and generating partner(s).

3. Once a KTP has been drafted and reviewed, it will be opened up for feedback from the Executive Committee.

4. ERINN will work with all relevant partners to assist where possible in the translation of KTPs into exploitation activities. The nature of these exploitation activities will be highly dependent on the KER, the target user, the transferring partner, the timeline, resources available and other variable considerations. The exploitation activities themselves may be carried out within a range of externally-focused tasks.

4. Dissemination and Communication Activities

The purpose of PREP4BLUE's communication activities are to make the project, its results and activities known to society at large so that all stakeholders, including those beyond the project's own community, will be able to understand its messages. All PREP4BLUE partners will dedicate time to perform communication activities and will be encouraged to engage in a two-way exchange with the public at large, and where possible the media, with the aim to show how EU research and innovation funding has a positive impact on society. Through its communication activities, PREP4BLUE will demonstrate why working together in a European consortium is important in addressing a challenge that affects all societies.

A key component of the PREP4BLUE communication strategy is co-development by ongoing engagement with key stakeholders and as the project progresses, it will be critical to ensure that the project outcomes are effectively and efficiently transferred to the relevant applications by policy, community, and research users, etc. A distinct strategy will be applied to each targeted audience, using appropriate messages, means, and language. In order to effectively promote and spread awareness about the PREP4BLUE concept and results so as to achieve the expected impacts, the following communication tools and activities (Table 3.) will be designed and implemented by the consortium and coordinated and monitored under T1.5. All PREP4BLUE communication activities will be captured in the PREP4BLUE Continuous Reporting Log which is available on the project Teams channel.

Table 3. Communication and dissemination activities and resources

TOOLS	Academics	Industry	Citizens	Civil Society	Policy makers	Other
PREP4BLUE Project Website	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
<p>The project website constitutes the main communication tool as it provides easy access to a broad audience around the world. The website will be designed and continually updated following the best practice guidelines for EU project websites.</p> <p>Target: 20,000 visits over the 3-year project duration</p>						
Project Factsheet	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
<p>A project factsheet (both printed and electronic versions) is available for distribution in relevant events and meetings for raising awareness about the project and triggering the interest of stakeholders to visit the website and stay informed about the project's progress. The project factsheet can be translated to relevant languages and updated towards the end of the project to highlight key results.</p> <p>Target: The factsheets will reach more than 5,000 people overall.</p>						
Press releases		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
<p>Press releases will be produced regularly making use of a range of services and publications aiming at increasing awareness about the project's objectives, progress and outcomes.</p> <p>Target: 6 press-releases to be published and put up to CORDIS wire leading to publication of at least 14 articles in the press and specialised publications like research.eu.</p>						
Promotional articles		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
<p>Promotional articles will also be regularly produced on project progress, highlighting project news, results and updates. These articles will be shared on the project website, throughout social media, in relevant magazines and stakeholder networks.</p> <p>Target: 40 promotional articles will be written and posted on the project website and shared with other networks and websites.</p>						
Video	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
<p>At least one project video will be produced as part of the project, for example providing an introduction to the project and its objectives, as well as project outcomes and how the project is contributing towards the Mission implementation.</p> <p>Target: The video will be viewed by more than 1,000 people</p>						
Social Media and Campaign	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
<p>The project Twitter account targets the general audience as well as specific targeted stakeholders. All project partners' social media outlets will share content and point out the relevance for their specific target groups, and thus direct their audience to PREP4BLUE channels and website. By adding relevant hashtags (such as #HorizonEU, #MissionOcean, #EUMissions, #BlueEconomy) PREP4BLUE reach will be further amplified.</p> <p>Target: The social media accounts will reach more than 5,000 people</p>						
Events and Workshops	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
<p>The consortium will participate in at least 10 conferences, with different target audiences. A number of national, European and international events will be targeted for dissemination activities including side events, webinars and online campaigns. Target: The PREP4BLUE events will target > 4,000 people, while attendance at other event will reach > 3,000 people</p>						

Scientific Publications	✓					
The consortium will aim to publish 5 open access articles over the four-year project. A selection of science, industry and social science publications will be identified that are the most appropriate. Target: 5 open access articles						
Newsletters	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
The consortium will publish an annual newsletter. Project news and updates will be shared to target science, industry, policy actors and the general public. Target: 3 annual newsletters to reach > 500 people						

5. PREP4BLUE-Specific Stakeholder Events

5.1 Citizen Engagement

T3.3 will focus on developing capacity building to mobilise and empower citizens to best engage with the Mission. This will be achieved via training, workshops and toolkits for Mission initiatives so that they can empower and activate citizens (M12 & D3.2). Capacity building activities will include the delivery of at least 4 expert-led workshops, and associated resources addressing a number of elements that are critical for impactful citizen action.

T3.4 will leverage the citizen engagement tools and methodologies developed in T3.1-T3.3 by organizing new citizens' network seeding events and supporting groups and networks to undertake pilot initiatives that engage with Mission priorities over the lifetime of the project (e.g., a restoration initiative in the Atlantic-Arctic Lighthouse; an anti-pollution initiative in the Mediterranean).

5.2 Physical and Virtual Mission Spaces

T2.3 will involve the design and piloting of innovative physical (events/exhibitions) and virtual (website) Mission Spaces for the Mission community and general population. The task will organise at least two public events in iconic spaces (e.g., Ocean Space | Venice) with artists, designers, architects, the European Bauhaus, and other initiatives to showcase the Mission and its contributors. The website developed under this task, will feature innovative and engaging features while simultaneously allowing project partners to showcase success stories (videos, feature stories) as well as practical information (events, papers, calls to action, funding opportunities, etc.) for the public.

5.3 Co-Creation Events

To make the Mission's relevance intuitively clear to European citizens, regardless of age, education, gender, ethnicity or background, WP2 will host at least two workshops/interactive events (in different LH Basins) specifically targeting the Mission contributors (internal), but with activities open to all interested parties - the first one ideally taking place early in the project in conjunction with a visible event. Moderated by professional media and social science experts, and including designers, artists, activists, etc., the workshops will support the development of guidelines with the main Mission slogan/motto, key messaging regarding what the Mission actually is, and key concepts, definitions, and ideas (in line with official Mission documents).

5.4 Pilot Stakeholder Assemblies for the Mission

Up to 4 pilot stakeholders' assemblies will be carried out, one per LH based area, to test and validate the methodologies developed in WP6, namely "D6.1 Stakeholder engagement guidelines, including toolkit". The identification of locations of interest for the pilots at each basin will be done through an analysis of the PREP4BLUE Mission Ecosystem Database (WP4), as well as the basin baseline studies or the implementation charters signed for the Ocean, Cities or Climate Missions, aimed at profiling relevant stakeholders across different scales and sub-sectors and mapping their interlinkages. Lessons learnt from these pilots will be published in the report "D6.3 Report on the findings of the stakeholder assembly's engagement pilots".

PROTOCOL – Public Outreach Activities – Internal and External Events

- Partners should inform the Project coordinator and ERINN of their planned outreach activities.
- Partners should inform other partners about the event through Teams/email, and it will be added to the shared calendar accessible to all partners.
- All activities, including attendance at external events should be added to the Continuous Reporting Log, providing insight on type of activity, audience type, reach (number of people) and other requested information.
- All public engagement and outreach activities must be reported during (internal and external) reporting periods.
- ERINN will include events on the PREP4BLUE website.
- ERINN will update the EC Portal on all Dissemination Activities.

6. External Events

All partners have a responsibility to engage the public in their activities and results and take advantage of the potential for public interest that PREP4BLUE generates. Partners are encouraged to initiate dissemination activities that are appropriate for their respective contributions and ERINN can provide support as required.

The project results will also be presented as oral presentations, posters, etc. at major international meetings and conferences of relevance to PREP4BLUE. Conferences, seminars, workshops, and other meetings are very useful forums to consult with PREP4BLUE target audiences in a face-to-face capacity and to address issues relevant to the work done in the project. International and sector relevant conferences, meetings, etc. will be frequently attended to communicate the results of the project to the maximum number of persons.

Table 2 shows a list of potential events that may be of interest to PREP4BLUE partners or stakeholders. These events will be added to the project website.

Table 4. Relevant events for PREP4BLUE consortium and stakeholders.

Event	Location	Date
European Mission Forum	Europe	Annually
World Water Day	Global	Annually in March
World Earth Day	Global	Annually in April
World Biodiversity Day	Global	Annually in May
World Environmental Day	Global	Annually in June
World Ocean Day	Global	Annually in June
World Maritime Day	Global	Annually in September
IUCN World Conservation Congress	Global	Every 4 years
World Water Week	Global	Annual Month TBC
European Week of Regions and Cities	Regional	Annually in October
European Research & Innovation Days	Brussels	Annually
European Maritime Day	Europe wide	Annually in May
Mediterranean Water Forum	Europe	Every 3 years
New European Bauhaus Festival	Europe, Global	Annual Month TBC
UN Ocean Conference	Global	Every 2 years

7. Dissemination and Communication Resources

The EC has developed specific Mission collateral including logo and branding, style guide, and related communication strategy. PREP4BLUE partners have been encouraged to utilise Mission Restore Our Ocean and Waters branding and logo when communicating with the public on the Mission. WP2 will determine when and how these resources should be used to promote PREP4BLUE results and outputs. For dissemination of the PREP4BLUE project, funding, partners as well as activities and initial results, a complementary logo and branding has been developed. This clearly aligns PREP4BLUE with the Mission and identifies it as a Mission initiative. If you have questions about when or how to use PREP4BLUE versus Mission Ocean specific branding, please contact KDM or ERINN.

7.1 Logo

The project logo is an integral part of the brand as it is included in all project’s promotional material.

The PREP4BLUE project logo is available in three different versions, full colour, black and white – see Branding Guide for details. The suite of logos is available on teams and can be requested from T1.5 leader ERINN (sarah@erinn.eu). Guidance on how to properly utilise the PREP4BLUE logo can be found in the Brand Guidelines, which will be available in the same location.

Figure 4. PREP4BLUE logo

PROTOCOL – Utilising PREP4BLUE Branding alongside other Institutional Branding

While it is preferable that all partners use PREP4BLUE branded resources when disseminating the project’s results, we recognise that some institutions will require partners to use their own institutional branding for conferences and various presentations. To balance the interests of PREP4BLUE, and our contractual obligations to the EC, with various institutional requirements, we require the following requirements to be included at minimum:

- The PREP4BLUE logo must be included on at least the Title Page and Conclusion/Thank You slide, however usage on all slides would be preferred.
- The EU emblem and disclaimer (Section 9.3) must be visibly present on the first and last slide.

7.2 PREP4BLUE Promotional Materials

PREP4BLUE PowerPoint and Poster templates, Factsheet and Slide Deck have been developed to use at internal and external events when presenting the PREP4BLUE project and/or its outcomes and can be downloaded from Teams.

PROTOCOL – PowerPoint Template

Partners should use the PREP4BLUE template when promoting the project’s objectives or presenting project results. WP2 will determine when the Mission specific branding should be used to promote and raise awareness of project outputs and success stories.

Download the template from Teams or contact sarah@erinn.eu or maura@erinn.eu.

- When using the PowerPoint template, choose to insert “new slide” and pick your preferred content template.
- Respect the template format (background, font and layout).
- Always ensure that the correct EU Emblem, acknowledgement, and disclaimer is present on any PREP4BLUE presentations.
- Partners are asked to provide a copy of any new template slides they develop.

Factsheet

A promotional factsheet presenting the PREP4BLUE objectives and expected results has been developed. The factsheet can be shared digitally and distributed at relevant events, both virtually and in-person. The factsheet is used to raise awareness of the project and its goals. It is available on the PREP4BLUE website or teams and can be requested from T1.5 leader ERINN (sarah@erinn.eu and maura@erinn.eu).

Partners are encouraged to distribute the factsheet through their networks and at relevant events. If partners wish to have the factsheet available in another language, they should follow the protocol outlined below:

PROTOCOL – Factsheet Translations

Contact ERINN (contact person: sarah@erinn.eu and maura@erinn.eu) requesting the original template with English text.

- ERINN supplies a template with the original text in English to requesting partner.
- Partner translates text (as laid out in the template) into their language.
- Partner then sends translated text back to ERINN.
- ERINN applies the translated text to the leaflet template and publishes the new version of the leaflet, after validation and sign-off from the partner responsible for the translation.

7.3 Press Releases and Newsletters

Press releases will be issued to appropriate media outlets (trade press, journals, web portals) to ensure that industry, communities, civil society, policymakers, and the wider community are aware of the project, its objectives and its later outcomes. The strategy is intended to ensure that there is media coverage at local, regional, European and international levels. T1.5 leader ERINN will share project news through internal (consortium mailing list and partner networks) and external channels (press releases, social media, project newsletter, etc.) which ensures a broad awareness of the project across the spectrum of relevant stakeholders. Partners are encouraged to publish articles and press releases at regional, national, and international levels, making use of their own communication networks and channels. ERINN can support partners in these activities.

PROTOCOL – Press Releases

Partners should notify ERINN if there is news suitable for an official project press release:

- ERINN will develop a draft and seek approval from the PREP4BLUE Coordination team
- Once approved, press releases will be disseminated using appropriate channels
- They will be uploaded to the project website and all partners are encouraged to distribute at national or regional level
- Where necessary the partners can adapt the press releases to customise them to their audience and if needed translate the articles

NOTE: Partners may also initiate the writing of press releases (e.g. local, national). ERINN can then support writing and editing if required. Partners are asked to provide a short summary in English if the original communication is in another language. Partners who publish any article/press release at a regional or national level must send a copy to ERINN and where possible provide metrics to demonstrate uptake by other news channels/readership.

7.4 Project Website

The project website, (<https://www.PREP4BLUE.eu/>) has been developed following the EU's best practice guidelines for project websites. The website is fully compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (EU 2016/679, GDPR) by incorporating a privacy statement and cookie bar informing website visitors about what PREP4BLUE does with any personal data gathered. Google Analytics is used to track traffic and monitor the use of the website, which will be used to inform Continuous Reporting.

To ensure successful promotion of the project and to sustain the interest of the target audience and attract new users, the website's content will be maintained, continuously updated and populated with new information through the project's lifetime. The website will remain live for five years after the end of the project, serving as a valuable public resource of research information on the subject and promoting the outputs of this publicly funded research.

PREP4BLUE has also created a second website through WP2, which will promote Mission Ocean to the public as well as serve project partners by hosting tools and information to aid both (feature stories, press releases, videos, important links to resources, tools, etc.). WP2 will work with other EU Missions (e.g., cities), living labs, citizen initiatives, etc. in order ensure inclusivity and populate the site with interesting and relevant content, as well as cutting edge technology and graphic features. Project partners are encouraged to share information on the site and WP2 will work with them to develop and/or post content.

PROTOCOL – Requests for Updates, Posting or any other Website Activity

Any partners who wish to upload materials, news or events to the PREP4BLUE website should contact sarah@erinn.eu or maura@erinn.eu. Partners who wish to add content to the Mission Ocean website should contact KDM.

Partners are requested to include a link to the PREP4BLUE website on their own institution/company website where possible.

7.5 Social Media

Social networking is an integral part of the PREP4BLUE communication strategy. The project results and outputs will be actively disseminated through Twitter. Stakeholders are encouraged to follow PREP4BLUE social media, which are forums for engagement with interested parties and contribute to capacity building, showing partner expertise and knowledge through active discussions. More Social media activity is planned throughout the project, in line with specific stakeholder groups and their preferences in receiving information. However as of M6, the project currently has two Twitter accounts:

1. To disseminate the project activities: **PREP4BLUE - @prep4blue**
2. To Support the Mission Narrative: **MissionOceanWaters - @ourmissionocean**

As with other means of communication, attention should be paid to the content being shared on social media. The consortium should determine which information to keep private and which to

publish, where and to what extent. If you have questions about what is appropriate, please contact ERINN (sarah@erinn.eu or maura@erinn.eu) and KDM.

In order for PREP4BLUE to maintain its reputation and create an engaging and thriving online community, it will be necessary to effectively manage potential risks. The following are guidelines for all partners who participate in social media and apply whether partners are posting to the PREP4BLUE account, their own accounts or commenting on other accounts.

PREP4BLUE Internal Code of Social Media Conduct

Partners should try to contribute to social media channels where possible. Support can be requested from ERINN.

General Rules

- Ensure the content is yours to share (research or opinions) or acknowledge the source accordingly
- Ensure there are no IP issues
- Use appropriate tags and hashtags to acknowledge funding (see below)
- Do not use offensive language, argumentative or illegal content etc.
- If you communicate publicly about PREP4BLUE or PREP4BLUE-related matters, you must disclose your role within the project.
- Be professional, use good judgement and be accurate and honest in your communications; unprofessional language or behavior reflect poorly on the project, and may result in liability.
- Unless approved by the coordinator IFREMER, your social media name, handle and URL should not include PREP4BLUE project's name or logo.
- Be mindful around controversial subjects, where emotions may run high e.g., politics. It is important to show respect for others' opinions.

Twitter:

Partners wishing to communicate via the PREP4BLUE Twitter account have the following options:

- Send a short message (280 characters max) to T1.5 leader ERINN (email sarah@erinn.eu or maura@erinn.eu) who can post from the PREP4BLUE accounts on your behalf. Ideally, include an image or short video to make it more visually appealing
- Refer to PREP4BLUE by tagging the project (using @prep4blue) in your own tweets/posts; ERINN will always aim to retweet/share such posts
- Refer to the Mission by tagging @eumissionocean in your own tweets/posts. KDM will aim to retweet/share such posts.
- In all posts, there are handles and hashtags which should be included where possible e.g. @HorizonEU, @EUScienceInnov, @cinea_eu, #EUMissions, #MissionOcean, etc.

- Retweet/share PREP4BLUE posts through your personal and institutional social media accounts (Partners can feel free to share their personal and institutional social media handles with ERINN).

Tips

Social media is becoming increasingly visual — post pictures, videos, GIFs or data visualisations.

- Engage with your audience using replies, retweets or tags.
- Ask questions instead of making statements to drive conversation.
- Leverage existing social media presence e.g., the host institution, researchers, team members or other relevant organisation, and tag and follow relevant accounts, particularly EC accounts (i.e., @HorizonEU, @EUScienceInnov)
- Follow the news and use trending hashtags where appropriate
- Content could include the announcement of milestones, results, scientific publications, press releases, newsletters, etc. or when the project is featured at a conference or event.

It should be noted that in July 2023, the social media platform Twitter was rebranded as X. Advice was sought on whether PREP4BLUE should update all communications materials to reflect the name change. Following research carried out by ERINN, it was determined that the Twitter brand is still the mostly commonly recognised and culturally accepted name for the platform. The platform is undergoing a period of volatility where further changes to the brand or a reversal of the name change are possible. With that in mind, it was decided that the Twitter brand and logo would continue to be used on PREP4BLUE communications materials. ERINN will continually monitor the situation and update materials if required.

7.6 Project Video

A project video will be created in the final six months of the project to showcase the project outputs generated and will be published on the PREP4BLUE project website and added to video-sharing websites, as well as posted on the project's social media accounts. Partners will be encouraged to share the video with their wider networks.

7.7 Other Resources and Tools

Other promotional material can be developed as required, depending on budget availability and considering sustainability. Please contact ERINN (sarah@erinn.eu and maura@erinn.eu) with any other ideas for promotional material to support your communication and dissemination activities.

8. Requirements related to Dissemination

8.1 Pre-Dissemination Requirements

For all types of Publications, Dissemination and Communication Activities (including scientific publications, oral and poster presentations, non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications, etc.) where PREP4BLUE results or outputs are presented, the Prior Notice Procedure (protocol below) must be applied.

The main partner involved in the dissemination of results from the PREP4BLUE project (owned by one or several parties) must give the other beneficiaries at least 15 calendar days together with sufficient information on the results they will disseminate. (CA Article 8.4.2.3, GA Article 17 – Annex 5)

PROTOCOL – Prior Notice Procedure

Upload the planned publication (full draft, if possible, but at a minimum this must include an abstract and details on where it will be published or presented) to the project TEAMS Prior Notice folder and request ERINN (sarah@erinn.eu or maura@erinn.eu) to inform the partnership via email (including where to find the uploaded information) of their intent at least 15 calendar days before publishing (see above).

Partners have 15 days to object in writing to the author.

Any objection needs to be justified and precise suggested modifications given. An objection is justified if:

- It adversely affects protection of results/background of the objecting party
- Legitimate interests of the objecting party would be significantly harmed

Please send the objection to the author, and cc the following people:

ERINN: sarah@erinn.eu, maura@erinn.eu

If no objection is raised within this time, or if objections are addressed and accepted by the objecting partner, the publication may then be submitted.

8.2 Post-Dissemination Requirements

8.2.1 Continuous Reporting of Dissemination and Communication Activities

PREP4BLUE partners are encouraged to disseminate and communicate their findings to stakeholders. When disseminating project results, remember to give Prior Notice to all other beneficiaries (see PROTOCOL – Prior Notice Procedure – Section 3.1). As part of the EU contractual requirements, all scientific publications and dissemination and communication activities are reported as part of the continuous reporting of the project in the EC Funding and Tender Opportunities Portal (see note below). The following information is required for every communication and dissemination activity:

- **Type of activity** (specify number of activities per type): organisation of a conference or workshop, press release, exhibition, flyer, training, social media, website, communication campaign, participation in a conference, workshop or other event, video/film, brokerage event, pitch event, trade fair, participation in activities organised jointly with other EC funded projects, etc.
- **Type of audience reached** (specify the number of persons per type): scientific community, industry, civil society, the general public, policy makers, media, investors, customers.
- **Total funding** amount for dissemination and communication activities linked to PREP4BLUE spent until the time of reporting. We request that you record the total funding amount attributed to each dissemination activity inputted to the logs (please fill this in on the last column of the log). Total funding amount should include direct costs. For example, if a partner presents at a conference, the direct costs would include registration fees or hotel costs.

NOTE: Data on all Dissemination and Communication activities will be collated and uploaded to the EC Funding and Tender Opportunities Portal by ERINN. Beneficiaries do NOT need to upload this information to the portal. To successfully manage the communication and dissemination activities, we require all partners to routinely update the “PREP4BLUE Continuous Reporting Log” which will be shared with all partners and located on the Teams channel.

8.2.2 Continuous Reporting of Scientific Publications

Scientific publications’ citations must be uploaded to the EC Funding and Tender Opportunities Portal once they have been accepted for publication. This includes articles in journals, publications in conference proceedings/workshops, books/monographs, chapters in a book, thesis/dissertation, etc. There is currently one scientific publication planned based on the outputs of WP3.

NOTE: Publications will be collated and uploaded to the EC Funding and Tender Opportunities Portal by ERINN. Beneficiaries do NOT need to upload this information to the portal. Partners are encouraged to send their publications to ERINN (sarah@erinn.eu, maura@erinn.eu) as soon as available and no later than three months after the official publication date, see detailed instructions below.

PROTOCOL – EC Reporting on Publications and Dissemination and Communication Activities

- All partners will be required to keep track of all their scientific publications, and dissemination and communication activities during project implementation.
- The “PREP4BLUE Continuous Reporting Log” has been developed by ERINN to support the reporting of these activities. The Continuous Reporting Log has been shared with all partners.

- Partners should regularly contribute information to update the log, this contains separate worksheets to report on 1) Publications and 2) Dissemination & Communication activities.
- The log will be reviewed by ERINN for completeness and correctness at EC reporting periods.

NOTE: Please do not change anything directly on the EC Funding and Tender Opportunities Portal yourself in relation to dissemination or publication activities. ERINN will upload the communication and dissemination activities, and publications to the portal.

8.2.3 Datasets

PREP4BLUE partners are responsible for ensuring that any datasets associated with publications are openly accessible and uploaded to the EC Funding and Tender Opportunities Portal the associated publication is published. Beneficiaries do NOT need to upload this information to the portal. Partners are encouraged to send their datasets to ERINN (sarah@erinn.eu, maura@erinn.eu), alongside the associated publication as soon as available and no later than three months after the official publication date.

To support the management of PREP4BLUE datasets, we require all partners to routinely update the “PREP4BLUE Continuous Reporting Log” which will be shared with all partners and located on the Teams channel and ensure all relevant datasets are available there.

8.2.4 Patents (IPR) Reporting

PREP4BLUE partners are responsible for tracking their Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and innovation activities resulting from the project. Whenever new IPR has been filed (the EC recommends filing with the European Patent Office), partners are required to email those activities and IPR to ERINN (sarah@erinn.eu and maura@erinn.eu). ERINN will then be responsible for uploading the required information to the EC Funding and Tender Opportunities Portal.

The partners are required to provide ERINN with the following:

- Identification of IPR type and Confidentiality
- Type of IPR (Patent/Trademark/Registered Design/Utility Model/Other)
- Confidentiality (Yes/No)
- Application Title
- Embargo end date

Table 5. Overview of Continuous Reporting Procedures

Item	Action needed by acting partner	Partner Uploading to EC Portal
Scientific Publications	Log Publication in the ‘PREP4BLUE Continuous Reporting Log’. Send notice of publication to ERINN.	ERINN

Datasets	Log dataset in the 'PREP4BLUE Continuous Reporting Log'. Email ERINN the required information.	ERINN
Communication and Dissemination Activities	Regularly log all communication/ dissemination activities in the 'PREP4BLUE Continuous Reporting Log'.	ERINN
Patents/IPR	Email ERINN (sarah@erinn.eu and maura@erinn.eu) the required information.	ERINN

9. Key Principles Guiding the PDEC

9.1 Definitions and Terminology

The foundation of the PREP4BLUE PDEC is the knowledge management process which has been implemented from the start of the project and which informs communication, dissemination, and exploitation. PREP4BLUE distinguishes between communication, dissemination, and exploitation (knowledge transfer), in line with the European Commission (EC) definitions as follows:

Communication is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the project and continues throughout its entire lifetime. It is aimed at promoting PREP4BLUE and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about PREP4BLUE and the project's results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. Activities used for communication purposes are, for example, a public website, social media, or a newsletter.

Dissemination is the public disclosure of the project results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protection or exploiting the results), including scientific publication in any medium. It is the process of promotion and awareness-raising right from the beginning of a project. It makes research results known to various stakeholder groups (e.g., research peers, industry and other commercial actors, professional organisations, policymakers) in a targeted way, enabling them to use the results in their own work. This process must be planned and organised at the beginning of each project. Activities used for dissemination purposes are, for example, a public website, press releases, publications, and attendance at events.

Knowledge transfer and exploitation of results is more advanced than communication and dissemination and requires several steps including identifying exploitation mechanisms and activities, focused on identified end-users to ensure impact and uptake of the results.

9.2 Rights, Rules and Obligations Related to Results

This section outlines a brief summary of some key aspects of the rights and obligations relating to the protection of these results; however it is not an exhaustive summary. For further details on the project and Horizon Europe rules surrounding ownership and protection of results please refer to the Grant Agreement (GA) and D1.3 Data Management Plan (DMP; due in M6).

9.2.1 Ownership of Results

Results are owned by the beneficiary that generates them. Two or more beneficiaries' own results jointly if they have jointly generated them and it is not possible to establish the respective contribution of each beneficiary, or separate them, for applying for, obtaining, or maintaining their protection (GA Article 16 – Annex 5). The joint owners must agree (in writing) on the allocation and terms of exercise of their joint ownership (joint ownership agreement), to ensure compliance with their obligations under the GA. If valuable results are not protected, the Commission may under certain circumstances assume ownership of the results (see GA Article 16 – Annex 5 for further details).

9.2.2 Protection of Results

Each beneficiary has an obligation to protect its results. Beneficiaries which have received funding under the grant must adequately protect their results — for an appropriate period and with appropriate territorial coverage — if protection is possible and justified, taking into account all relevant considerations, including the prospects for commercial exploitation, the legitimate interests of the other beneficiaries and any other legitimate interests.

9.2.3 Exploitation of Results

Each beneficiary has an obligation to exploit its results. Beneficiaries which have received funding under the grant must — up to four years after the end of the action - use their best efforts to exploit their results directly or to have them exploited indirectly by another entity, in particular through transfer or licensing.

If, despite a beneficiary's best efforts, the results are not exploited within one year after the end of the action, the beneficiaries must (unless otherwise agreed in writing with the granting authority) use the Horizon Results Platform to find interested parties to exploit the results (see GA Article 16 – Annex 5 for further details).

9.2.4 Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and Management

PREP4BLUE will follow the rules for IP set out by the EC, as regulated. More information can be found in GA Section 2 (Article 16) "Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) — Background and Results — Access Rights and Rights of Use";

The partners will ensure that adequate steps towards protection are taken prior to exploitation, dissemination, and communication, preventing unapproved public disclosure of results, tools, products and services.

9.3 Dissemination of Results

9.3.1 Obligation to Dissemination

Each beneficiary must disseminate their results as soon as possible by disclosing them to the public. However, no dissemination may take place before a decision is made regarding possible protection (section 2.2.4). Other participants may object if their legitimate interests in relation to their foreground or background could potentially suffer harm.

Beneficiaries that intend to disseminate their results must give advance notice (prior notice) to the other beneficiaries, unless agreed otherwise, at least 15 calendar days advance notice to other beneficiaries (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results they will disseminate.

Any other beneficiary may object within (unless agreed otherwise) 15 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests.

Notwithstanding the above, certain dissemination activities which, by their nature, must be carried out in a timely manner (e.g. social media posts, promotional articles and reports) will be exempt from the obligation to give prior notice to all partners so as not to impede the project's dissemination strategy, provided that all PREP4BLUE beneficiaries engaged in such dissemination are in agreement prior to such dissemination and provided that the duty of confidentiality is respected (GA Article 13).

9.3.2 Open Access

Providing open access to publications in Horizon Europe funded projects is an obligation for all grants. Each beneficiary must ensure open access to all peer reviewed scientific publications relating to its results (GA Article 17 – Annex 5), and should:

As soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications; moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.

Ensure open access to the deposited publication, via the repository, at the latest:

- on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or
- within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.

Ensure open access, via the repository, to the bibliographic metadata that identifies the deposited publication: the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon Europe”; the name of the project, acronym and grant number; the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and a persistent identifier.

For more information on open access, please consult ANNEX 5 of the Model Grant Agreement, “HE Communication, Dissemination, Open Science And Visibility”. Further details will be outlined in the PREP4BLUE Data Management Plan (DMP).

9.3.3 Visibility of EU emblem

Partners are obligated to use the EU emblem when publishing and/or presenting work carried out under the PREP4BLUE project (GA Article 17.2). Unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must display the EU emblem. This includes conferences, seminars, in information material (such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc.), including electronic form via social media, etc. and any infrastructure, equipment or major result funded by the grant. When displayed in association with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the partners may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Agency. This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

Any communication activity related to the project must include the following disclaimer and emblem:

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union, through its Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101056957 (PREP4BLUE). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the granting authority, the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

If you have any queries about the use of this disclaimer, please contact ERINN Innovation (sarah@erinn.eu, maura@erinn.eu)

9.4 General Data Protection Regulation Implications

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU 2016/679) provides enhanced protection to individuals' data privacy rights. Organisations storing or using personal data (anything that allows identification of an individual) must clearly disclose what data is being collected and how, why it is being processed/used, how long it is being retained, and if it is being shared with any third parties. Personal data can be names, email addresses, job titles, phone numbers, and anything that allows identification of an individual.

9.4.1 Website

The PREP4BLUE project website (www.prep4blue.eu/) managed by ERINN Innovation, will be fully compliant with GDPR by incorporating a Privacy Statement and Cookie Bar and informing website visitors about what PREP4BLUE does with any personal data gathered. There will be a 'Sign up for news' button clearly visible on the Home Page, allowing people to voluntarily sign up to the PREP4BLUE mailing list. The sign-up page will contain a link to the Privacy statement, and subscription is on a double opt-in basis, whereby people who sign up need to confirm their email address to complete the subscription process. The subscription system will send an automatic PREP4BLUE email to the subscriber who then needs to click on the link in the email

sent to them. Using double opt-in ensures compliance regarding consent under GDPR. The mailing list will only be used to share PREP4BLUE related information and news.

10. Monitoring and Evaluation

Throughout the project, Task1.5 leader ERINN will continue to review and amend the PDEC in line with the deliverables on the exploitation and dissemination of results. These updates of the PDEC will include a summary of the activities carried out. As part of the revision process, each subsequent version of this deliverable will be validated by the consortium. Furthermore, the project coordinator and project partners will also review the PDEC at each review stage and provide recommendations. The current version (D1.6) will function as the operational manual. The next revision will be D1.9 (M36, May 2025).

11. Partners involved in the work

All partners are expected to carry out dissemination and exploitation activities as well as communication activities. ERINN will provide coordination and support to all activities.

Appendix II: Knowledge Output Template

KNOWLEDGE OUTPUT TEMPLATE
Knowledge Output Reference Number: CORDIS project code – KOa, KOb, KOc, KOd etc. <i>(the letter stands for several linked KOs of the same source) For internal use – should be completed by the fellow</i>
Knowledge Output Title: <i>Please provide a short and concise title to describe the KO.</i>
Project Code: <i>CORDIS Project Code</i>
Project/Publication Title:
Acronym/ short title:
Co-funding: <i>Please provide details of any co-funders (in addition to the EU) in relation to this project</i>
Knowledge Output Owners: <i>Please provide the name, organisation and contact details of the individual(s) who should act as the contact person for this KO. If the beneficiary/owner of the KO differs from the contact person then please indicate so.</i>
GDPR: <i>Is the knowledge output owner willing to consent to PREP4BLUE holding their contact details for the purposes of Knowledge Transfer activity only. Please indicate whether you have applied for IPR (patent, copyright, etc.) for this KO or not? If yes, please provide details.</i>
Status: <i>State the TRL/ SRL (Appendix 1).</i>
IP: <i>Is there a reasonable potential for commercial exploitation of this knowledge output? If so, please indicate if any plans to protect this KO have been considered or carried out.</i> If patented, include the patent number or trade-mark registration.
Knowledge Output Description (about 1 page): <i>Please aim to provide a full description, making the KO fully understandable to a non-expert. Consider the following flow of the narrative. This may vary depending on the type of Knowledge. This may include, but is not set in stone nor restricted to the following example content (outline for each just a paragraph):</i>
<p><i>Background</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Setting the scene (only 1-2 sentences).</i> <p><i>Technical description</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Key characteristics of the KO.</i> • <i>Current state of development (describe the readiness level). If it is a technology, how does it compare to what is currently used.</i> • <i>Innovativeness (what is innovative and/or new about it).</i> • <i>Progress beyond the current state-of-the-art/evidence base.</i> • <i>Justifying body of evidence (or are there contradictory results).</i> <p><i>Potential Impacts and Applications</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Specific policy or commercial applications.</i> • <i>Potential impacts, especially towards the mission objectives/ targets</i> • <i>Needs addressed.</i> • <i>Liaison(s) taken place with target users and/or end-users.</i>
Contextual Information: <i>Steps that lay within the responsibility of the Knowledge owner, that have been taken towards Pathways to Impact (further funding attracted or planned to attract or feasibility studies undertaken, market-studies undertaken, potential users contacted).</i>
Next steps: <i>Steps towards the Pathway to Impact that have not yet been taken and do not necessarily lay within the responsibility of the Knowledge Owner (e.g. further user identification, new applications etc.).</i>
<p>Other Information</p> <p><i>Is the KO described in a document or report which is open or restricted access (if there are no plans to make publicly available now or in the future please state Restricted Access; If possible please provide a link to the document (e.g. website address; Digital Object Identifier (DOI), scientific journal details, patent number, etc.).</i></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> <i>It is restricted access, for safe storage and not for public access only.</i></p>

It is open access. We are happy to share publicly the Knowledge Output Description – only the text shadowed in blue – on the ‘Mission Ecosystem Data Base’ (currently under development) in order to enhance the visibility of our knowledge. It will be only bade public after previous consultation before publication.